

Death Anxiety among Hospitalized Patients: A Gender Based Comparison

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Mr. Shahid Ali

M.Phil. Scholar, Department of Psychology, University of Balochistan, Quetta DOI:

Dr. Saima Ambreen

Chairperson/ Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology,
University of Balochistan, Quetta

Dr. Sara Mehmood Durrani

Lecturer, Department of Psychology, University of Balochistan, Quetta

www.jqss.org

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Abstract

Objectives: Present research purpose is to investigate and compare the level of death anxiety among male and female hospitalized patients in Balochistan. **Place and duration:** the research was conducted in various hospital of district Quetta and Makuran Division, Balochistan and took 6 months for completion. **Sample and methods:** Total sample for the study encompassed 50 hospitalized patients that includes male [n= 27, M (SD) = 51.41 (6.541)] and female [n=23, M (SD) = 49.04(6.630)] admitted in various hospitals of Balochistan. **Measure:** Informed Consent Form and Death Anxiety Scales (Donald Templer, 1970) was utilized for any level of death anxiety. **Analysis:** For assessing and comparing death anxiety among two gender groups. Descriptive analysis and independent sample t-test was conducted. **Results:** Results indicate substantial death anxiety among hospitalized patients of Balochistan, but there were non- significant differences among male and female on the levels of death anxiety.

Keywords: Death Anxiety. Hospitalized Patients, Anxiety, Gender Based, Quetta and Makuran

Corresponding Author Email:

shahidali05031987@gmail.com

saima.ambreen.awan@gmail.com

smdpsy@gmail.com